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LOCATION-BASED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS OF 2019 NIGERIA PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION USING A VOTING ENSEMBLE APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria president Buhari defeated his closest rival Atiku Abubakar by over 3 million votes. He was issued a Certificate of Return and was sworn in on 29 May 2019. However, there were claims of widespread hoax by the opposition. The sentiment analysis captures the opinions of the masses over social media for global events. In this paper, we use 2019 Nigeria presidential election tweets to perform sentiment analysis through the application of a voting ensemble approach (VEA) in which the predictions from multiple techniques are combined to find the best polarity of a tweet (sentence). This is to determine public views on the 2019 Nigeria Presidential elections and compare them with actual election results. Our sentiment analysis experiment is focused on location-based viewpoints where we used Twitter location data. For this experiment, we live-streamed Nigeria 2019 election tweets via Twitter API to create tweets dataset of 583816 size, pre-processed the data, and applied VEA by utilizing three different Sentiment Classifiers to obtain the choicest polarity of a given tweet. Furthermore, we segmented our tweets dataset into Nigerian states and geopolitical zones, then plotted state-wise and geopolitical-wise user sentiments towards Buhari and Atiku and their political parties. The overall objective of the use of states/geopolitical zones is to evaluate the similarity between the sentiment of location-based tweets compared to actual election results. The results reveal that whereas there are election outcomes that coincide with the sentiment expressed on Twitter social media in most cases as shown by the polarity scores of different locations, there are also some election results where our location analysis similarity test failed.

KEYWORDS

Nigeria, Election, Sentiment Analysis, Politics, Tweets, Exploration Data Analysis, location data

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TEXT SUMMARIZATION IN MONGOLIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Textual information in this new era, it is difficult to manually extract the summary of a large data different areas of social communication accumulates the enormous amounts of data. Therefore, it is important to develop methods for searching and absorbing relevant information, selecting important sentences, paragraphs from large texts, to summarize texts by finding topics of the text and frequency based clustering of sentences. In this paper, the author presents some ideas on using mathematical models in presenting the source text into a shorter version with semantics, graph-based approach for text summarization in Mongolian language.

KEYWORDS

graph representation, adjacency matrix, vector space, similarity measurement, quantum cognition, algorithm and encoding.

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EVALUATING BERT AND PARSBERT FOR ANALYZING PERSIAN ADVERTISEMENT DATA

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the impact of the Internet on modern trading and the importance of data generated from these transactions for organizations to improve their marketing efforts. The paper uses the example of Divar, an online marketplace for buying and selling products and services in Iran, and presents a competition to predict the percentage of a car sales ad that would be published on the Divar website. Since the dataset provides a rich source of Persian text data, the authors use the Hazm library, a Python library designed for processing Persian text, and two state-of-the-art language models, mBERT and ParsBERT, to analyze it. The paper's primary objective is to compare the performance of mBERT and ParsBERT on the Divar dataset. The authors provide some background on data mining, Persian language, and the two language models, examine the dataset's composition and statistical features, and provide details on their fine-tuning and training configurations for both approaches. They present the results of their analysis and highlight the strengths and weaknesses of the two language models when applied to Persian text data. The paper offers valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of working with low-resource languages such as Persian and the potential of advanced language models like BERT for analyzing such data. The paper also explains the data mining process, including steps such as data cleaning and normalization techniques. Finally, the paper discusses the types of machine learning problems, such as supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning, and the pattern evaluation techniques, such as confusion matrix. Overall, the paper provides an informative overview of the use of language models and data mining techniques for analyzing text data in low-resource languages, using the example of the Divar dataset.

KEYWORDS

Text Recognition, Persian text, NLP, mBERT, ParsBERT

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LEXIS AND SYNTAX OF MEDICINE PRODUCT WARNINGS IN THE PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

In the Philippines, parents refused their children having an anti-measles and anti-dengue vaccines, which created a medical outbreak. This may not happen if product warnings have been given and explained to the parents. Indeed, product warnings are found to be in their optimal position in safeguarding the life of consumer-patients. This paper anatomizes the lexical features of medicine product warnings in the Philippines which are crucial in the response discourses. A range of linguistic frameworks were applied and significant findings were drawn. Gaps were identified on the use of noun abstractness, synthetic personalization, field continuum, adjectives, and adverbs. Such an investigation brought up the transparency of communicative features of medicine safety texts. In the end, linguistic components create a vital impact on the legal content adequacy of medicine product warnings, unfolding the vitalities of these messages in facilitating informed decision-making among consumer-patients.

KEYWORDS

medicines, consumer-patients, linguistic components, product warnings.

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A STUDY ON THE APPROPRIATE SIZE OF THE MONGOLIAN GENERAL CORPUS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the appropriate size of the Mongolian general corpus. This study used the Heaps' function and Type-Token Ratio (TTR) to determine the appropriate size of the Mongolian general corpus. This study's sample corpus of 906,064 tokens comprised texts from 10 domains of newspaper politics, economy, society, culture, sports, world articles and laws, middle and high school literature textbooks, interview articles, and podcast transcripts. First, we estimated the Heaps' function with this sample corpus. Next, we observed changes in the number of types and TTR values while increasing the number of tokens by one million using the estimated Heaps' function. As a result of observation, we found that the TTR value hardly changed when the number of tokens exceeded 39~42 million. Thus, we conclude that an appropriate size for a Mongolian general corpus is 39-42 million tokens.

KEYWORDS

Mongolian general corpus, Appropriate size of corpus, Sample corpus, Heaps' function, TTR, Type, Token.

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SENTIMENT ANALYSIS IN MYANMAR LANGUAGE USING CONVOLUTIONAL LSTM NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been an increasing use of social media among people in Myanmar and writing review on social media pages about the product, movie, and trip are also popular among people. Moreover, most of the people are going to find the review pages about the product they want to buy before deciding whether they should buy it or not. Extracting and receiving useful reviews over interesting products is very important and time consuming for people. Sentiment analysis is one of the important processes for extracting useful reviews of the products. In this paper, the Convolutional LSTM neural network architecture is proposed to analyse the sentiment classification of cosmetic reviews written in Myanmar Language. The paper also intends to build the cosmetic reviews dataset for deep learning and sentiment lexicon in Myanmar Language.

KEYWORDS

Social Media, Sentiment Analysis, Convolutional LSTM.

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Full Text: <https://airconline.com/ijnlc/V10N4/10421ijnlc02.pdf>

NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING THROUGH THE SUBTRACTIVE MOUNTAIN CLUSTERING ALGORITHM — A MEDICATION INTAKE CHATBOT

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the subtractive mountain clustering algorithm has been adapted to the problem of natural languages processing in view to construct a chatbot that answers questions posed by the user. The implemented algorithm version allows for the association of a set of words into clusters. After finding the centre of every cluster — the most relevant word, all the others are aggregated according to a defined metric adapted to the language processing realm. All the relevant stored information (necessary to answer the questions) is processed, as well as the questions, by the algorithm. The correct processing of the text enables the chatbot to produce answers that relate to the posed queries. Since we have in view a chatbot to help elder people with medication, to validate the method, we use the package insert of a drug as the available information and formulate associated questions. Errors in medication intake among elderly people are very common. One of the main causes for this is their loss of ability to retain information. The high amount of medicine intake required by the advanced age is another limiting factor. Thence, the design of an interactive aid system, preferably using natural language, to help the older population with medication is in demand. A chatbot based on a subtractive cluster algorithm is the chosen solution.

KEYWORDS

chatbot, medicine intake aid system, natural language processing, subtractive mountain clustering.

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MACHINE-READABLE ENTAILMENTS WITH THE ITALIAN PRENDERE CONSTRUCTION EXPRESSING HITTING AND INSULTING EVENTS

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ABSTRACT

The Italian language features a little debated transitive construction with *prendere* ‘to take/to catch’ in which a prepositional phrase (PP) with an adverbial value occurs mandatorily (e.g. *Lui prese a pugno Leo* ‘He punched Leo’). Semantically, this construction often implies the use of physical force or verbal offence. In the hitting or insulting event, the notional subject generally is a [+ Human] Agent, whilst the notional direct object generally is a [+ Animate] Affectee ([1]: 4). It can be contended that *prendere*, which carries no literal meaning, is zero-valent and that the predicate assigning semantic roles is the PP. A computational tool will be illustrated, which automatically performs the following NLP / NLU tasks: it provides a reliable syntactic and semantic representation of the clause type, and it produces machinereadable entailments with three clause types, i.e. sentences with ordinary verbs, support verbs, and the causative verb *fare* ‘to make/to have’.

KEYWORDS

Natural Language Processing, Recognizing Textual Entailment, Semantic Role Extraction, Adverbial PPs with a predicative value, Support verbs.

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DRIVING PRODUCT SALES PERFORMANCE BY ANALYSING PRODUCT PRELAUNCH IN A LINGUISTICS APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This paper uses a natural linguistics analytic approach, by studying product prelaunch events' script, to investigate the determinants of driving the product sales based on customer values framework as well as "Nextopia" consumer psychology. This research contributes to the theoretical framework of identifying the customer values, which have impacts on the product sales. Moreover, we investigate how product sales be driven by the optimism attitude and affective forecasting feeling, which are vocal during product prelaunch events. Through the study of analysing the essential words, which represent the underlying customer values from the script of Apple Inc. product prelaunch events, we found that product functional and experiential/ hedonic of customer values drive product sales. Induced affective forecasting message negatively moderated the impact of cost/ sacrifices values on product sales. In addition to the theoretical contributions, this research provides practical guidelines of how to shape the product prelaunch speech to maximize the sales of the to-be-released products.

KEYWORDS

Product Preannouncement, Product Sales, Signalling, Communications, Speech Recognition.

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A SENTIMENT LEXICON-BASED ANALYSIS FOR FOOD AND BEVERAGE INDUSTRY REVIEWS. THE GREEK LANGUAGE PARADIGM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to implement a methodology to detect and quantify customers' opinions which referred to the Food and Beverage (F&B) sector using the Greek language. Due to the large and continuously opinionative data produced by the evaluations of the customers' reviews, the F&B companies, and/or other stakeholders face difficulties to extract all the necessary data and to proceed to further analysis. As far as the Greek market is concerned, the F&B sector is one of the most dynamic sectors. Delivery or take away food or coffee is very common, with the vast majority of consumers to order from aggregators' platforms (online digital markets). In this study, 8,950 customers' reviews are extracted from 690 companies selected randomly from a total of 6,795 companies covering the most popular capitals of Greece and presented in the most used common e-platform. The mining of customers' reviews covers a month period during the year of 2018 and the evaluated functions are the quality of food, the customer service, the image of the company, the pricing, and the quantity of food. As it appears, the sentiment analysis in an aspect-level using the lexicon-based technique should approach methodologically the problem by identifying not only the relevant information but also the particular expressions and phrases the evaluators use over the Internet. The extracted keywords and phrases from the customers' reviews are used to form the corresponding dictionaries of the functions and to proceed in the sentiment classification. The method is tested in an annotated dataset of 2,000 customers' reviews and, overall, the findings are expected to contribute towards the design and implementation issues of a sentiment lexicon particularly devoted to the Greek F&B industry.

KEYWORDS

Sentiment analysis; modern Greek; Food & Beverage Industry; Aspect-level; lexicon-based; corpus-based.

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